

Multielement analysis of soil and plant species using wavelength-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry

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Abstract : In the present study, a sequential wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (WD-XRF) method for the quantitative analysis of 11 elements (Al, Fe, Mg, Ca, Na, K, As, Co, Cr, Cu and Zn) in soil and plant species has been developed. Certified reference materials were used to calibrate and evaluate an analytical method for the determination of major and trace elements in soils, while for plant species a qualitative scanning method which displays peak and element identification, taking into account the typical element contents in different plant specimens was performed. A calibration procedure was estimated by employing six plant samples for obtaining a quantitative XRF method based on empirical calibration mode. The samples were prepared as pressed pellets, and analysis was performed within a total measuring time of 15 min per sample. The detection limits obtained for the trace elements (1–2 mg/kg) are adequate both for geochemical and environmental purposes and the accuracy of the method is within the expected interval of certified values in most cases. On the whole, analytical performance of the WD-XRF method proposed proved to be effective and robust.

Keywords : WD-XRF, soils, plant species, reference materials.

Introduction

The concentration of major and trace elements in plants are governed both by the geochemical features of the soil where the plant grows and by the ability of plants to accumulate elements selectively. Moreover, plants can accumulate elements from surrounding aerial or aquatic environment, enabling some plants to be used as biomonitors^{1–3}. The chemical analysis of soils can reveal anomalous high metal values and help authorities to the presence of polluted elements in the ecosystem originating from natural sources such as mineralization of a specific rock or metals found in runoff from mines or in effluents from industries, etc. However, in many soils the true threat to an ecosystem may be obscured by the chemical analysis of a total soil sample with respect to environmental pollution monitoring^{4,5}. Hence, it is important that the analytical procedures used should be rapid and appropriate in accuracy and precision in analyte concentration determination.

Concerning the analytical techniques that can be used, probably one of the most appropriate is X-ray fluores-

cence (XRF) spectrometry. Several reasons explain the wide acceptance of XRF, not the least being sample preparation, instrumental precision, and longevity of calibrations. Commonly, plant analysis has been carried out by means of spectroscopic techniques, including flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS), inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES), and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Each of these techniques have its own advantages and disadvantages in terms of analytical performances. In such cases, X-ray methods may provide a useful alternative for metal alloy/plant analysis which allow for a matrix destruction stage^{6–8}. Simplicity of sample preparation, minimum manipulation, speed and the chance of analyzing even elements such as sulphur and chlorine.

In general, XRF quantitative analysis is carried out by the calibration curve method, obtained with many calibration standards. However, for some applications (such as plant species) it is difficult to get a sufficient number of certified standards with similar matrices of the samples to achieve a good range of data points for each element to be determined⁹. Nevertheless, recent improvements in

XRF instrumentation with a better excitation and detection capability has added the advantage of increased instrumental sensitivity, thus resulting in improved precision and productivity. This has promoted an increasing interest in using X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy in the field of environmental analysis as an alternative to a destructive analytical method. The purpose of the present study was to develop a quantitative analytical XRF method for the routine analysis of soil and plant samples, prepared as pressed pellets. In such an application, the homogeneity and particle size of the powders can significantly influence the quality of the final results.

Experimental

Instrumentation and operational parameters :

Soil and plant analysis :

A Philips MagiX PRO, Model PW 2440, wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer, coupled with an automatic sample changer PW 2540 and provided with suitable software SUPER Q 3.0 for soil analysis and IQ+ software for plant analysis, was used for this study (Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands). The MagiX PRO is a sequential instrument with a single goniometer based measuring channel covering the complete elemental measurement range from F to U in the concentration range from 1.0 ppm to % level, determined in vacuum. The instrument is microprocessor controlled for maximum flexibility and consists of an end-window X-ray tube with an Rh anode and a maximum voltage/current of 60 kV/125 mA at a maximum power level of 4 KW. The κ - α analytical lines and instrumental parameters used for each element are as per instrumental manual.

Sampling and pre-treatment for WD-XRF analysis :

All soil samples were used as received without drying because of concerns about loss by volatilization. Pressed pellets (40 mm diameter) were prepared by using collapsible aluminium cups^{10,11}. These cups were filled with boric acid and about 2 g of the finely powdered soil sample after mixing and pressed under a hydraulic press at 25-ton pressure to get a pellet (Hydraulic Press, Herzog, Germany).

To study the applicability of XRF for trace element analysis of a few plant species, *Eichornia crassipes* (leaves), *Oryza sativa* (roots), *Capparis sepriaria* (leaves),

Calotropis gigantean (twigs), *Prosopis juliflora*, and *Spinacia oleracea* (whole plant), growing in and around an industrial area, were collected¹². The plant species were washed thoroughly with deionized water to remove superficial dust and were then oven-dried at 60 °C for 24 h. To reduce particle size and to satisfy the conditions for homogeneity, the dry ash plant powder was then ground in an agate ball mixer mill for 5–10 min. Dry ashing consists generally in calcination of the sample in a muffle furnace which ensures the decomposition of organic matter at temperatures between 450 °C and 550 °C. The advantage of dry ashing procedures is the ability to treat large sample amounts and dissolving the resulting ash in acid. In this study, an attempt was made to take the ash powder of each sample 2 g without binder and prepare a pressed pellet at 25 tons cm² pressure for 60 s to obtain a circular 40-mm diameter. Then, each pellet was placed on a sample holder directly facing the X-ray beam of the XRF spectrometer for elemental determination.

Calibration :

The spectrometer was calibrated after measuring intensities of 22 international reference materials (see listing in Table 1). The criteria to select these samples were the required interval of concentration, the quality of the known data for each reference material, and also previous calibration tests. Source/reference for the certified values was taken from Govindaraju¹³.

Results and discussion

Soils :

Calibration lines were obtained with the SUPER Q 3.0 analytical software issued by the instrument manufacturer and using linear regression of the net intensities versus concentration. For elements like As and Cd the matrix effects were corrected using empirical coefficients, more specifically alphas, based on count rate. Geological reference materials, i.e. those with reference values and associated uncertainties for almost every element present at detectable concentrations, are common for silicate matrices. When reference materials with abnormally high concentrations of trace elements are considered, there are too few available reference values and their associated uncertainties to permit calibration of the spectrometer. As a consequence, difficulties arise when samples with

anomalous high concentrations of one or more elements are to be determined.

The results obtained for major and minor elements in a group of reference materials are presented in Table 1. Two lines of data are presented for each sample. In the first line, the results are presented with the associated uncertainty, calculated during analysis. The second line represents certified values of the reference materials. The uncertainty includes the sum of the following components : counting statistics, systematic errors in background calculation, and spectral correction and sensitivities used to calibrate the spectrometer. Counting statistics is the dominant source of uncertainty for trace elements. All data were obtained for single pellet analysis, but some pellets were analyzed two or three times, and this instrumental uncertainty is of the same order as that presented with the data.

Detection limits :

An important statistical consideration in XRF analysis is the capability of an instrument to merely detect whether an element is present in a specimen or not. In fact, one wants only to be able to claim with some defined statistical certainty that a given element is present if its concentration is greater than a certain limit¹⁴. These studies using the PW 2440 spectrometer enabled us to scan the elements of interest and to calculate the counting statistical error (CSE) and the lowest limit of detection (LLD) for selected counting times on peaks and backgrounds. When reasonable times are selected (60 peak – 40 background for trace elements and 20 peak – 10 background for major elements) the LLD and CSE are good.

Precision :

Precision of triplicate analysis is expressed as the relative standard deviation (%RSD). Although the RSD varies from sample to sample and for each element, the range of RSD based on the highest and lowest concentrations gives a good indication of the precision at high concentration levels. Fig. 2 shows the RSD of the element concentration measured for major and trace elements, the RSD is well below 5%, except for K showing 5.7% for SRM-2710, SRM-2711, and 5.65% and 5.48% for samples BCR-141R and BCR-142R, respectively. However, for trace elements, the RSD is also below 5% for some elements like Co, Cu, Zn and Zr, and above 5.52% for As,

5.07% for Cr, and 5.32% for Ni. Attempts were made to correct matrix effects with empirical alphas based on concentration which did produce acceptable calibration. When based on intensities, matrix correction was achieved by trial and error and was mainly based on which elements would more strongly absorb the emitted intensities of the element of interest. Matrix corrections based on empirical coefficients are only valid for the analysis of samples with a composition within the interval of standard. For this reason, for some heavy metals, reference materials with unusually high concentrations were also included as standards.

Accuracy :

The accuracy of the results was evaluated by comparison with the certified values of the analyzed reference materials. When the certified values are known, the results should ideally be within the confidence interval : $CV \pm CI$. Some reference materials used in the present work contain anomalous concentrations of one or more elements and the results obtained are presented in Table 1. The major elements Al_2O_3 and MgO in SRM-2709 have certified values only and are not within the 95% confidence interval.

The limiting factor in the final accuracy of XRF analysis of common geological samples is the lack of information concerning constituents not usually determined by XRF. The most important of these are water and carbon (present either as carbonate or as organic carbon). For example, according to a study performed by Jacinta *et al.* in 2004², the reference material NIST SRM-2710, for which the data are provided on the certification by the suppliers, contains 3% (mass fraction)m/m C. When this value for C is used in the fundamental parameter calculations, the Zn result obtained is 6900 ± 20 mg/kg; which is within the $CV \pm CI$ value of 6952 ± 91 mg/kg. When the C content was omitted, a higher result was obtained : 7190 ± 10 mg/kg. In many geoanalytical laboratories, water and carbon are not determined but just estimated in sum from loss on ignition (LOI). Comparing major and trace element results, the latter showed a tendency towards better results. This can be attributed to the fact that trace elements tend to be better characterized in soil samples and also because trace elements are less affected by mineralogical effects when analyzed in pressed pellets.

Table 1. Analytical results obtained for major (% oxide form) and trace elements (mg/kg) using WD-XRF

Sample	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	CaO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	As	Co	Cr	Cu	Zn
SRM-2709	16.5±0.2 14.17	5.1±0.01 5.00	3.1±0.10 2.50	2.52±0.09 2.64	1.24±0.02 1.56	2.35±0.014 2.45	16.1±0.8 17.7	17.2±0.8 13.4	106.6±2.0 130.0	35.7±0.5 34.6	109.0±0.9 106.0
SRM-2710	12.4±0.36 12.16	4.86±0.01 4.83	1.45±0.02 1.41	1.57±0.04 1.75	1.43±0.01 1.54	2.52±0.14 2.54	606.8±7.7 626	13.8±0.8 10.0	40.2±0.8 39.0	2513±6.0 2950	5359±11.8 6952
SRM-2711	12.10±0.10 12.34	3.92±0.02 4.13	1.96±0.05 1.74	3.64±0.12 4.03	1.39±0.03 1.54	2.93±0.17 2.95	461.6±6.4 105	12.7±1.2 10.0	44.3±1.6 47.0	104.1±0.6 114.0	316.4±1.4 350.4
TILL-1	13.33±0.40 13.7	6.37±0.45 6.82	2.09±0.11 2.15	2.27±0.38 2.72	2.30±0.46 2.71	2.03±0.21 2.22	17.5±0.8 18.0	17.6±0.66 18.0	64.4±0.60 65.0	46.5±0.64 47.0	97.5±0.61 98.0
TILL-3	11.40±0.72 12.2	3.73±0.21 3.92	1.33±0.32 1.71	2.50±0.10 2.63	2.43±0.48 2.64	2.23±0.15 2.42	86.4±0.6 87.0	14.5±0.58 15.0	121.5±1.5 123.0	21.5±0.28 22.0	55.5±0.7 56.0
BCR-141R	10.93±0.45 **	3.30±0.08 **	1.34±0.04 **	14.60±0.61 **	0.43±0.01 **	1.83±0.10 **	14.8±0.8 **	10.9±1.3 10.5±0.4	191.9±1.4 195±7	46.3±1.8 46.4±1.8	281.0±0.5 283.0
BCR-142R	19.72±0.30 **	4.68±0.01 **	2.03±0.05 **	1.36±0.04 **	1.76±0.03 **	2.89±0.18 **	23.5±0.8 **	15.9±0.9 12.1±0.7	112.7±1.2 **	73.5±0.6 69.7±1.3	109.5±0.4 **

First row values of each sample were obtained in this work (± 1S, n=3). Second row values are certified values, issued by the producers of the reference materials. ** Values not provided.

Table 2. Comparison of data obtained by XRF with ICP-MS analytical data

Sl. no.	Plant species	Cr (mg/kg)		Mn (%)		Co (mg/kg)		Ni (mg/kg)		Cu (mg/kg)		As (mg/kg)		Pb (mg/kg)	
		ICP-MS	XRF	ICP-MS	XRF	ICP-MS	XRF	ICP-MS	XRF	ICP-MS	XRF	ICP-MS	XRF	ICP-MS	XRF
1.	<i>Eichornia crassipes</i>	11.5	13.86	0.07	0.92	11.0	14.6	71.8	69.74	72.5	68.56	0.6	19.37	94.7	93.79
2.	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	10.1	16.45	0.09	0.94	21.6	20.62	23.3	26.07	60.7	41.99	3.2	16.4	88.5	90.37
3.	<i>Capparis septaria</i>	57.3	54.58	0.08	0.71	14.5	12.44	13.7	12.45	75.8	23.05	4.2	4.61	34.0	36.88
4.	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	19.6	17.12	0.07	0.52	9.5	4.19	49.5	52.29	50.9	91.56	0.4	12.57	73.0	75.83
5.	<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	36.7	45.14	0.01	0.35	1.8	1.1	17.8	20.47	41.8	69.98	1.4	11.5	62.8	67.86
6.	<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>	44.7	51.16	0.02	0.53	64.2	70.41	37.3	41.6	55.8	33.94	7.0	41.39	130.6	133.92

Plant species :

Qualitative analysis :

Qualitative analysis and spectral identification was carried out by using the qualitative scanning mode linked to the equipment, which includes automatic peak and element identification (IQ+ standardless software) provided with the equipment. This kind of analysis enables the analyst to obtain multi-elemental information and appears to be an effective means for primary screening of any sample. A set of 33 plant samples were analyzed using the qualitative scan and elemental concentration in % were recorded for major and trace elements (Al, Fe, Mg, Ca, Na, K, As, Co, Cr, Cu and Zn). Compiling the data for all elements a set of six samples were chosen based on maximum concentration obtained for each element. For example, Fig. 1 shows a qualitative spectrum obtained for one plant species by using the qualitative scanning

mode. The scan was repeated for an additional five plant species in a similar manner. Then the peak angle was fixed based on sensitivity, relative intensities, lower limit of detection (LLD), and counting statistical error (CSE).

Quantitative analysis :

In general, XRF quantitative analysis is carried out by the calibration curve method generated from measurements made with many calibration standards. However, some applications such as for plant species it is difficult to get sufficient certified standards with matrices similar to the samples, in order to achieve a good spread of data point over the range of each element to be determined. In such cases, the use of standard less quantitative procedures are commonly applied⁶. In the case of plant species samples, the absorption of the measured X-rays by the matrix is relatively small compared to other heavier samples (i.e. rock or soil). Nevertheless, due to the widely

Fig. 1. Qualitative scan of plant species *Eichorina crassipes* (leaves).

Fig. 2. The relative standard deviation (RSD) on y-axis for trace elemental concentration and numbers on x-axis indicate standards 1 : SO1, 2 : SO3, 3 : SO4, 4 : SRM-2709, 5 : SRM-2710, 6 : SRM-2711, 7 : TILL1, 8 : TILL3, 9 : BCR-141R, 10 : BCR-142R.

variable range of concentrations of K, Ca, Cl, and other elements in plant samples, correction for the matrix effects is necessary in order to obtain quantitative results. Calibration lines were obtained with the SUPER Q 3.0 analytical software issued by the instrument manufacturer and using linear regression of the net intensities versus concentration. For some elements (As, Pb, Ni) the matrix effects were corrected using empirical coefficients, more specifically α -corrections, based on count rate. The validation of the procedure was performed by comparison with data obtained using an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS)¹² (Table 2). The elements Pb, Cr, Co, and Ni were found not to be significantly different in the concentration with an almost 97% confi-

dence limit. However, at the same confidence levels, some statistical differences were found for Mn, As, and Cu. For these elements, this could be due to appreciable amounts of silicon which would not have been digested evenly and would have been in the colloidal form in plant species, especially in the case of leaves¹⁰. In such conditions, according to the literature, some elements could not be recovered (especially Al, Fe, Cu, and Mn) due to the binding of the analytes with the silica residue.

Conclusion

The analysis of soils by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry is advantageous because little effort is necessary in sample preparation. The analysis method proposed is very

robust since reliable results could be obtained for a representative set of major and trace elements in several distinct types of geochemical reference materials with anomalous concentrations of many elements. The accuracy of the method, when only major elements are considered, improves from lighter to heavier elements. In this work, the usefulness of a wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (WD-XRF) method for the sequential determination of the elements Na, Mg, Al, Si, P, S, K, Cl, Mn, Fe, Cu, Ni, Zn, Cr, Co, Cd, and As in plant samples was tested. The precision and accuracy of the proposed method was evaluated by comparing the data with the analytical data of plant species obtained by ICP-MS. In contrast, the WD-XRF methodology proposed shows the analysis method to be robust since reliable results were obtained for a representative set of major and trace elements in several distinct types of plant species.

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